

PROPERTIES OF EPOXY RESIN TREATED BY STRONG MAGNETIC FIELD

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SUMMARY: The effect of strong static magnetic field (SMF), i.e. magnetic field with constant strength in time to 19 T, on the epoxy resin, traditional matrix for composites has been studied. SMF exerts a substantial influence on the process of curing of epoxy resin resulting in an anisotropy of its structure and properties. The effect of SMF resulted in an anisotropic linear thermal expansion coefficient and shift of glass-transition temperature. The wide-angle X-ray scattering showed a shift of the peak of the amorphous halo. The microhardness of cured epoxy resin with an increase in field strength attained the maximal level at approximately 8T.

KEYWORDS: epoxy resin, magnetic field, matrix, composite, structure, property.

INTRODUCTION

On the basis of earlier studies¹ the behavior of polymer molecules in SMF can be described in simplest case in terms of a model of rigid asymmetrically shaped noninteracting particles, which possess anisotropy of magnetic susceptibility $\Delta\chi$, and present in a low viscosity medium. Due to high values of $\Delta\chi$, calculated for nonaromatic molecules by Pascal's additive scheme, polymer chains could be oriented by SMF. Aromatic molecules are characterized by elevated $\Delta\chi$, caused by presence of so called ring current. In common the degree of orientation of macromolecules in a low-viscosity medium exposed to SMF depends on the ratio of the magnetic and thermal energies.

However, if hardening of epoxy resin is carried out directly in SMF, then a result of the chemical-addition reaction there occurs a successive and predominant selective fixation of the structural state. SMF arrange reactive groups in a kinetically favourable order. As a result, the energy in SMF is enough to overcome the disorder and to connect the reacting groups of

oligomer with the growing chain creating the additional bonds and order in the cross-linked polymer.

EXPERIMENTAL

The object of investigation was an epoxy compound of diglycidyl ether of diphenylolpropane with 10% polyethylene polyamine as a curing agent. Components were mixed at 50°C. Then compound was cured in Teflon cups at the room temperature $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 45 min in the bore of the superstrong electromagnet with intensity to 19 T (Fig. 1a). Specimens had the form of discs 10 mm in diameter and 3 mm thick at various SMF. Magnetic field experiments were conducted at the High Field Magnet Laboratory at the University of Nijmegen (The Netherlands).

Diffraction of x-rays of epoxy specimens was studied on a DRON-3M diffractometer with the use of transmission photography method in the interval of angles $2\Theta = 8-60^\circ$. The diffraction patterns were recorded in the equatorial direction parallel to SMF vector and in the meridional direction perpendicular to SMF. For an exact determination of the angular position of the peaks of the diffuse maxima, scanning of the angular ranges of the amorphous halos with the step of 0.1° and with the pulse rise time at each step of 60 sec was carried out. The error of determining the angular positions of the peaks in such scheme did not exceed 0.05° .

The dilatometric curves of epoxy samples in the direction parallel and perpendicular to the vector of SMF were recorded on the UIT-70M device for investigating thermomechanical properties of polymers. Linear feeding of the specimen was carried out at a rate of $2.5^\circ\text{K}/\text{min}$ up to 520°K . Cooling occurred according to exponential law. The dilatometric feeding and cooling curves are recorded on x-y recorder.

The tests of microhardness H were conducted on an PMT-1 mashine. The specimen was loaded by 100 g on the indenter in direction perpendicular to the surface of sample and parallel to the vector of SMF. Each point on the curves represents the mean of 30-50 indentations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Fig.1b shows the typical distribution of microhardness H in the bore of electromagnet at a field induction $B = 8,5 \text{ T}$. The distribution of SMF intensity in the bore is very inhomogeneous with maximal point in the center of longitudinal axes of the bore. The magnetic field increases microhardness maximally at the maximal field point. The same picture of distribution is observed for other intensities of SMF. It means that the influence of magnetic field on the curing process of epoxy resin is very strong, and in other our experiments the results of measurements of epoxy samples cured at maximal field point are presented. Dependence of microhardness at maximal field point H_{max} on the induction of field B is shown at the Fig. 3.

Figure 2 shows dilatograms of heating and cooling of epoxy specimens treated by SMF of induction $B = 8, 5 \text{ T}$ which were taken in the directions parallel (B_0) and perpendicular (B_{90}) to the direction of magnetic field intensity. The exothermic peaks at glass-transition temperature T_g are observed on the heating curves. Under influence of SMF there is a shift of T_g toward the region of higher temperatures. The intensity of peak in direction perpendicular to \mathbf{B} is smaller than in the direction of SMF. It means that there is an anisotropy in the net structure. Dependence of this shift of T_g on the induction of field B is shown at Fig. 3.

Teflon cups with epoxy resin

Fig. 1: Scheme of experiment (a) and distribution of microhardness H along the axis of bore of electromagnet L (b).

The X-ray diffraction pattern taken of specimen polymerized under standard conditions has the typical amorphous halo with maximum at $2\Theta = 19.80 \pm 0.05^\circ$. It means that as result of hardening the totally disordered spacial net tied by chemical bonds has been created. Under the action of the SMF there is some shift of the peak of the amorphous halo toward large angles. Dependence of this shift on the induction of field B is shown at Fig. 3. The shift is due to the cross-linking processes in the material under the effect of SMF and occurrence of internal stresses related to them.

Fig.3 shows the dependence of the errors of determinations of changes in angular position of X-ray diffraction peak $\Delta 2\Theta$, of glass transition temperature T_g , and microhardness H_{max} on the field strength B . These parameters with an increase in field strength attained the maximal level at approximately 8T.

Fig. 2: Dependence of microhardness H_{max} (—) , the shift of X-ray diffraction peak (.....) , the shift of glassy temperature ΔT_g (—) on the induction of field B .

Fig. 2: Dilatograms of heating (1) and cooling (2) of epoxy specimens treated by SMF of induction $B = 8, 5T$ which were taken in the directions parallel (B_0) and perpendicular (B_{90}) to the direction of magnetic field intensity and control sample ($B = 0$).

The achieved results has shown the possibility of changing the physical-mechanical properties of thermoset polymers by SMF treatment. The process of curing of epoxy resin in SMF can be described in terms of liquid crystalline polymers². The hole process is very complicated because the process of LC orientation is disturbed by formation of chemical bonds. The achievement of saturation value for SMF effect can be explained by competition of these processes.

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